

THE PERCEIVED ROLE OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE SERVICES IN THE PREVENTION AND CONTROL OF CHOLERA AMONG BWARI RESIDENTS, ABUJA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, a satellite town within Nigeria's Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The objectives were to assess whether immunization, Essential drugs, Maternal and child health care are perceived roles of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents. The descriptive research design using the multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. The sample population comprised of Four hundred and fifty five residents. The instrument used for the study was a researcher developed questionnaire which was validated by three experts in related field and tested for reliability. Test re-test method was used to obtain the reliability of the instrument. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to obtain a correlation coefficient result of $r = 0.75$. The instrument was administered by the researchers and two trained research assistants. Inferential Statistics of Chi-square was used to test the three research hypotheses set for the study at 0.05 alpha level, using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0. The findings of the study revealed that: immunization is a perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera because calculated χ^2 value (429.7) > critical value (21.03); Essential drugs is a perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera because calculated χ^2 value (207.03) > critical value (21.03); Maternal and child health care is a perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera because calculated χ^2 value (80.55) > critical value (21.03); This study concluded that immunization, supply of essential drugs and maternal and child health care are significant perceived roles of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera. It was therefore recommended that Primary Health Care Services should intensify efforts in the routine immunization exercise, improve on their services in the area of supply of essential drugs and ensure that the drugs are available and affordable, Women using Primary Health Care Services should be educated on the need to observe simple hygiene and should be taught how to administer Oral Rehydration Therapy (ORT) whenever the need arises.

Keywords: fever, immunization, sanitation, hygiene, cholera, prevention

INTRODUCTION

Cholera is an infection of the small intestine that is caused by the bacterium *Vibrio cholera*. The main symptoms are profuse watery diarrhea and vomiting. Transmission is primarily through consumptions of contaminated water or food. The severity of the diarrhea and vomiting can lead to rapid dehydration and electrolyte imbalance (Okon, 2014). Every year there is an estimated 3-5 million cases of cholera

that results in about 100,000-120,000 deaths. The short incubation period which ranges from two to five days, enhances the potentially explosive pattern of outbreaks. Cholera transmission is closely linked to inadequate environmental sanitation (Cholera Annual Report, 2011). Typical areas at risk include semi-urban slums, where basic infrastructure are not readily available, as well as camps for internally displaced persons

or refugees, where minimum requirements of clean water and sanitation are not met. The consequences of a disaster such as disruption of water and sanitation systems, or the displacement of populations which leads to inadequate water supply and overcrowded camps can increase the risk of cholera transmission. Cholera is an ancient disease like tuberculosis.

Although the disease may be mild, severe cholera can cause dehydration, renal failure and death within hours of onset. World Health Organization (2013) submitted that Cholera is a contagious infectious disease that is characterized by extreme vomiting, profuse watery diarrhea and leg pains. It has been found that transmission transpires mostly via absorption of contaminated drinking water or food. The health of an infected person disintegrates rapidly and death may occur if treatment is not promptly given. Cholera was first discovered in the Indian subcontinent in 1817. The disease reaches all the way through Asian continent in the 1960s, getting in to Africa in 1970 and Latin America in 1991. In many parts of Africa and Asia, the disease is still endemic. Cholera is a disastrous water-borne infectious disease that is caused by the bacterium *Vibrio cholerae*. It is a very serious problem in many developing countries including Nigeria due to

inadequate access to safe drinking water supply, improper treatment of reservoirs and improper environmental sanitation. In 2012, WHO reported 245,393 cholera cases and 3034 death cases across 48 countries in which 67% cases occurred in African countries (WHO, 2013). In 2005, Nigeria had 4,477 cases and 174 deaths. There were reported cases of cholera in 2008 in Nigeria in which there were 429 deaths out of 6,330 cases. Furthermore, 304 cases were reported in Niger State in which 114 death cases reported (Abiodun, 2014). Also in 2009, Nigeria reported 691 cases and 431 deaths (Okon, 2014). Cholera is an acute enteric infection caused by the ingestion of bacterium *Vibrio cholerae* present in faecally contaminated water and food. Primarily linked to insufficient access to safe water and proper sanitation, its impact can be even more dramatic in the areas where basic environmental infrastructures are disrupted destroyed. Countries facing complex emergencies are particularly vulnerable to cholera outbreaks. Massive displacement of Internally Displaced Persons, refugees and overcrowded settings, where the provision of potable water and sanitation is challenging, constitutes also a risk factor. In consequence, it is of paramount importance to be able to rely on accurate surveillance data to monitor the evolution of the outbreak

and to put in place adequate intervention measures and co-ordination of the different sectors involved is essential. (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control, 2014).

Cholera is characterized in its most severe form by a sudden onset of acute watery diarrhea that can lead to death by severe dehydration. The extremely short incubation period - two hours to five days - enhances the potentially explosive pattern of outbreaks, as the number of cases can rise very quickly. About 75% of people infected with cholera do not develop any symptom. However, the pathogens stay in their faeces for 7 to 14 days and are shed back into the environment, possibly infecting other individuals. Cholera is an extremely virulent disease that affects both children and adults. Unlike other diarrhoeal infections, it can kill healthy adults within hours. Individuals with lower immunity, such as malnourished children and people living with HIV, are at greater risk of death if infected by cholera (WHO, 2015). Outbreaks are linked to the consumption of unsafe water and food, poor hygiene and sanitation.

Cholera often follows natural or man-made disasters which can lead to internal displacement of persons and subsequent unstable living conditions associated with contamination of food and water sources (Shikanga, Mutonga, Abade, Amwayi, Ope, Limo, Mintz, Quick, Breiman & Feikin, 2008).

Overflowing of latrines and contamination of wells and surface water, seasonal modification of water sources for consumption and human behaviour may play a role in the occurrence of cholera outbreaks. Control of cholera outbreaks requires effective surveillance and response systems which are frequently sub-optimal in developing countries often lacking robust data collection, collation, analysis, interpretation and responses. Poor detection and delay responses to cholera outbreaks can result in geographical spread of the disease and consequently high mortality and morbidity rates. Failure to control local outbreaks and prevention of cholera between regions could result in spread of cholera outbreaks to neighboring regions (Telmessani, 2010). Drinking any infected water and eating any foods washed in such water, as well as consumption of shellfish living in the affected waterway can cause a person to cholera infection (Marin, Thompson & Freitas, 2013).

According to National Health Policy on Primary Health Care Services and in line with Alma-Ata declaration (1978), the functions of Primary Health Care Services include the followings:

Immunization, Maternal and Child Health Care, Provision of Essential drugs. Oral cholera immunization is increasingly used as an additional tool to control cholera outbreaks in combination with the traditional

interventions to improve safe water supply, sanitation, hand washing and other means to improve hygiene conditions. Since licensure of Dukoral and Shanchol, over a million doses of these immunization exercises have been deployed in various mass oral cholera campaigns around the world and in addition, oral cholera immunization was incorporated in the public health programme and over 9 million doses have been administered through targeted mass vaccination or immunization of school-aged children in cholera endemic regions. The cholera vaccine is largely used by backpackers and persons visiting locations where there is a high risk of cholera infection. However, since it does not provide 100% immunity from the infection, food hygiene precautions should also be taken into consideration when visiting an area where there is a high risk of becoming infected with cholera. Although the protection observed has been described as "moderate", herd immunity can multiply the effectiveness of vaccination. Dukoral has been licensed for children 2 years of age and older, Shanchol for children 1 year of age and older. The administration of the vaccine to adults confers additional indirect protection (herd immunity) to children. WHO recommends that current available cholera vaccines be used as complements to traditional control and preventive measures in areas where

the disease is endemic and should be considered in areas at risk for outbreaks. Vaccination should not disrupt the provision of other high priority health interventions to control or prevent cholera outbreaks. Reactive vaccination might be considered in view of limiting the extent of large prolonged outbreaks, provided the local infrastructure allows it, and an in-depth analysis of past cholera data and identification of a defined target area have been performed. World Health Organization (WHO) recommends that immunization which is currently available against cholera infection be used in conjunction with the usually recommended control measures in areas where cholera is endemic as well as in the areas at risk of outbreaks. Oral vaccine has been shown to provide short-term protection of 85-90% against *V. cholera* O1 among all age groups at 4-6 months following immunization with minimal side effects (WHO, 2013).

Bwari residents experience regular cases of cholera infections which could be severe and sometimes result in death especially in places like Mpape; an Urban – Slum in Bwari Area Council of FCT, Abuja. (NCDC, 2014). The researchers observed that cholera infection among Bwari residents, Abuja are caused majorly by contamination of water and poor environmental conditions and

many of the residents are not aware that they could get help in the areas of adequate water supply and environmental sanitation from the Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera. It is also observed by the researchers that many Bwari residents, Abuja suffers from diarrhea and vomiting which are not unconnected with vibrio cholerae that has led to serious health problems and deaths among Bwari residents as it was reported by Vanguard news paper (2014) that no fewer than 11 residents have died of cholera leaving over 40 hospitalized in Mpape a community in Bwari Area Council, Abuja.

It is also observed by the researchers that there is high level of indiscriminate dumping of refuse and open defecation among Bwari residents, Abuja which led to the spread of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja. These are just few cases of cholera that have been reported and several other cases were not reported. Therefore, this study has necessitated the need to assess the perceived roles of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised in order to find answers to the research problem:

1. Is immunization a perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja?

2. Is supply of essential drugs a perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja?
3. Is maternal and child health care a perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. Immunization is not a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.
2. Supply of essential drugs is not a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.
3. Maternal and child health care is not a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.

Methodology

The research design adopted for the study was a descriptive research design of the survey type. The study population comprises of four hundred and fifty five (455) respondents selected using multi-stage sampling technique was used for

the study through stratified sampling, random sampling technique and purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for the study was a developed questionnaire titled perceived role of primary health care services in the prevention and control of cholera among bwari residents, Abuja. that was validated by three experts in related field and tested for reliability. Test re-test method was used to obtain the reliability of the instrument. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to obtain a correlation coefficient result of $r=0.75$. The instrument was administered by the researchers and two trained research assistants. Inferential Statistics of Chi-square was used to test the three research hypotheses set for the study at 0.05 alpha level, using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.0.

Results

The findings from the study were tracked in line with the set objectives of the study.

1: Immunization is not a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis Showing Environmental Sanitation as a Perceived Role of Primary Health Care services in the Prevention and Control of Cholera.

2: Supply of essential Drugs is not a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care services in the prevention and control of cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.

Table 2: Chi-square Analysis Showing Supply of essential Drugs as a Perceived Role of Primary Health Care services in the Prevention and Control of Cholera.

3: Maternal and Child Health Care is not a Significant Perceived Role of Primary Health Care services in the Prevention and Control of Cholera among Bwari Residents, Abuja.

Table 3: Chi-square Analysis showing Maternal and Child Health Care as a Perceived Role of Primary Health Care Services in the Prevention and Control of Cholera among Bwari residents, Abuja.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1, shows that 305(69.1%), 315(69.2%), 260(57.2%), 263(57.9%) and 300(65.9%) of the respondents were of the opinion that immunization is a perceived role of PHCS, PHCWs provides adequate immunization, PHCWs immunization adults only, PHCWs immunization both children and immunization PHCWs is effective for the prevention and control of cholera. The findings from the analysis in table 3 shows the calculated Chi-square (x^2) value of 429.7 against the table value

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row	Cal. χ^2	df	Crit. Value	Remarks
1	Immunization is part of the perceived role of PHCS in the prevention and control of cholera	43 (9.5%)	262(57.6%)	122 (26.8%)	28 (6.2%)	455	429.7	12	21.03	Rejected
2	PHCS provides adequate immunization for the prevention and control of cholera	142 (31.2%)	173 (38%)	121 (26.6%)	19 (4.2%)	455				
3.	PHCS immunize only adults for the prevention and control of cholera	75 (16.5%)	185(40.7%)	161 (35.4%)	34 (7.5%)	455				
4.	PHCS immunize both children and adults for the prevention and control of cholera	38 (8.4%)	225 (49.5%)	162 (35.6%)	30 (6.6%)	455				
5.	The immunization given by PHCS is effective in the prevention and control of cholera	56 (12.3%)	244 (53.6%)	135 (29.7%)	20 (4.4%)	455				
	Column Total 0.05 alpha level of significance	354	1089	701	131	2275				

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row Total	Cal 2	Df	Crit. Value	Remarks
10	Maternal and child health care is part of the perceived role of PHCS in the prevention and control of cholera	95 (20.9%)	226 (49.7%)	123 (27.0%)	11 (2.4%)	455	80.55	12	21.03	Rejected
11.	Pregnant women, nursing mothers and children are adequately treated of cholera	59 (13.0%)	191 (42.0%)	183 (40.2%)	22 (4.8%)	455				
12.	PHCS attitude discourages women from receiving treat of cholera from Primary Health Care centres	43 (9.5%)	167 (36.7%)	209 (45.9%)	36 (7.9%)	455				
	Column Total 0.05 alpha level of significance	197	584	515	69	1365				

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	Row Total	Cal 2	Df	Crit. Value	Remarks
6.	Supply of essential drugs is part of the perceived role of Primary Health Care workers in the prevention and control of cholera.	78 (17.1%)	244 (53.6%)	116 (25.5%)	17 (3.7%)	455	207.03	9	16.92	Ho Rejected
7.	The drugs provided by the Primary Health Care workers in the prevention and control of cholera are grossly inadequate	75 (16.5%)	229 (50.3%)	137 (30.1%)	14 (3.1%)	455				
8.	The essential drugs provide by the Primary Health Care workers in the prevention and control of cholera is affordable.	50 (11.0%)	218 (47.9%)	176 (38.7%)	11 (2.4%)	455				
9.	The drugs given by the Primary Health Care workers in the treatment of cholera are effective.	67 (14.7%)	228 (50.1%)	147 (32.3%)	13 (2.9%)	455				
10.	Column Total 0.05 alpha level of significance	270	919	576	55	1820				

of 21.03 at 0.05 alpha level with degree of freedom 12. Since the calculated χ^2 value of 429.7 is greater than the table value of 21.03, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, which means immunization is a perceived role of PHCS in the prevention and control of cholera.

Table 2, shows that 322(70.7%), 304(66.8%), 268(58.9%) and 295(64.8%) of the respondents were of the opinion that supply of essential drugs, the drugs supply are inadequate, the essential drugs are affordable and the drugs given by the PHC workers are effective for the prevention and control of cholera respectively. The findings from the analysis in table 3 shows the calculated Chi-square (χ^2) value of 295.40 against the table value of 16.92 at 0.05 alpha level with degree of freedom 9 Since the calculated χ^2

value of 207.03 greater than the table value of 16.92, thus, the null hypothesis was rejected, which means supply of essential drugs is a perceived role of PHCS in the prevention and control of cholera.

Table 3, shows that 321(70.6%), 250(55.0%) and 210(46.2%) of the respondents were of the opinion that maternal and child health care, pregnant women, nursing mothers and children and the attitude of PHC workers discourages women from receiving treatment of PHC workers nation and control of cholera respectively. The findings from the analysis in table 5 shows the calculated Chi-square (χ^2) value of 80.55 against the table value of 21.03 at 0.05 alpha level with degree of freedom 12 Since the calculated χ^2 value of 80.55 greater than the table value of 21.03, thus, the null

hypothesis was rejected, which means maternal and child health care is a perceived role of PHCS in the prevention and control of cholera.

Conclusion

The study concludes that: Immunization is a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera. Supply of essential drugs is a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera., Maternal and child health care is a significant perceived role of Primary Health Care Services in the prevention and control of cholera.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

- i. Primary Health Care workers should carry out routine immunization programmes on the quarterly basis among pregnant, nursing mothers, children and other residents of Bwari Area Council, Abuja to prevention and control spread of cholera.
- ii. Primary Health Care workers should improve on their services in the area of supply of essential drugs and ensure that the drugs are available and affordable for the Bwari residents to prevent and control of cholera.

- iii. Women using Primary Health Care Services should be educated on the need to observe simple hygiene and they should be taught on how to administer Oral Rehydration Therapy (ORT) whenever the need arises.

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